

ISic3166

I.Sicily inscription 3166

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia, hypogeum M1

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329742

1. Χρῆστος ἔζη-
2. σεν ἔτη κζ' □ καὶ
3. ἔτελεύτα καλ (άνδαις)
4. Νοβ (εμβρίαις) □ νυμφίος.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645496

PHI 329742

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 15.0582

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 236 ph

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.

Vatican. At no.303

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